

Key or Nomenclature of Brian Paul Kaess' Texts

Key or Nomenclature for some of Brian's written stuff/texts:

KNV = *Kaess Family from the Neckar Valley* (2019)

KOS = *Kaess/Ochiltree/Swartz Family History* (2017)

KD= *Kaess/Dawson Family* (2016)

NKF= *Notes on the Kaess Family* (2016)

HGB= *Haller/Gibboney/Baldwin Family* (2015)

DUS= *The Dorschkes of Upper Silesia: A Genealogy* (2026)

TBM= *The True History of Brian Paul Kaess in Mexico: From 2006 to 2025* (2026)

KM= *Kaess Miscellany* (2025)

TEN= *"What It Is, Not What It Ain't! Escalating Tensions in the Mexican Drug War"* (2025)

BK= *Brian Paul Kaess Autobiography* (2025)

S1-8= *Selected Essays of Brian Paul Kaess: Volumes 1-8* (2025) EX: Selected Essays Volume 1 would be S1.

R1-3= *Remaining Essays of Brian Paul Kaess: Volumes 1-3* (2026) EX: Remaining Essays Volume 1 would be R1.

FR= *Fragments & A Manichaeon Harmony* (2025)

FRII= *Fragments II & Another Manichaeon Harmony* (2025)

FRIII= *Fragments III & a 3rd Manichaeon Harmony* (2025)

FRIV= *Fragments IV* (2026)

FRV= *Fragments V* (2026)

MUP= *Mayte Urbina Pereda: A Life between Roses and Revolution* (2025)

GK= *Garret Thomas Kaess: From Poverty to Prestige—A Life of Grit, Genius, and Global Reach* (2025)

KSS= *The Kaessaron* (2025)

DEL= *Delomelanicon Italian-to-English Translation* (2025)

HP= *Handbook of Poetry* (2026)

Add.= *Addendum* EX: Kaess/Dawson Family Addendum 4 p. 3 would be KD Add. 4:3